

Taxonomy of Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School, Inc

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Abstract:-This research was concerned with identifying, classifying, naming, and providing a botanical description of the angiosperms present in Saint Louis School Inc. located on Quirino Highway, Baguio City, to raise the awareness of students and personnel on present angiosperms. It is concerned with suggesting ways how to preserve and conserve the different flowering plant species present in the school vicinity. There are 44 plant species identified belonging to 26 families namely Acanthaceae (2), Alstromeriaceae (1), Amaryllidaceae (3), Apocynaceae (4), Araceae (2), Asphodelaceae (1), Asteraceae (4), Begoniaceae (2), Bignoniaceae (2), Bromeliaceae (1), Caryophyllaceae (1), Convolvaceae (1), Crassulaceae (1), Ericaceae (1), Euphorbiaceae (1), Geraniaceae (2), Lamiaceae (3), Lythraceae (1), Malvaceae (2), Melastomataceae (1), Nyctaginaceae (1), Orchidaceae (2), Rosaceae (1), Rubiaceae (2), Solanaceae (1), and Verbenaceae (1). Plants belonging to Apocynaceae and Asteraceae have the highest number of plant species. Only a general way of conservation of angiosperms was provided. As a result, a follow-up study on specific ways how to conserve plants that will cater to their different needs is highly recommended. Based on the results, Saint Louis School Inc. is filled with diverse beautiful angiosperms. It is important to maintain, put effort into conserving these flowering plants, and have a deeper appreciation towards them, especially as learners and personnel of SLSI.

Keywords:- Angiosperm Conservation, Apocynaceae, Asteraceae, Flowering Plants, Taxonomy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The branch of science associated with describing, identifying, and classifying organisms is referred to as taxonomy. Taxonomy is derived from the Greek words “taxis” which means arrangement, and “nomia” meaning methods or distribution. Both alive and extinct organisms are classified in this branch of biology [24]. As stated by the [30] Convention on Biological Diversity (2009), “taxonomy provides basic understanding about the components of biodiversity which is necessary for effective decision-making about conservation and sustainable use” (para.1). In the explanation of Sunderland in 2015, everyone is an inherent taxonomist. People classify things

around them, just like how taxonomists distinguish species in biodiversity. They find out what separates one species from another so they can distinguish and categorize these organisms to easily communicate biological information [23]. Sunderland (2015), summarized the importance of this branch as “taxonomy provides the basic foundations of conservation practice and sustainable management of the world’s remaining resources. It is perhaps time to better integrate the science of taxonomy back into the conservation world to meet the global biodiversity challenge that we currently face” (para.7) [23].

Taxonomy poses many benefits and advantages to the ecosystem and aid in the growth of countries all over the world. An example of this is its aid in the development of New Zealand. The Benefits of Taxonomy (2015) stated that “There are many benefits of taxonomy to New Zealand because taxonomic knowledge underpins New Zealand’s economic, environmental, social and cultural fabric” (para.1). Taxonomy aids in New Zealand’s economic benefit through obtaining market access for fish, identification of pests, pathogens, and biological contaminants for food safety, and improving the country’s resilience by identifying species with attributes that will be suited to climate-changing conditions. Taxonomy also provides effective biosecurity through accurately identifying invasive organisms such as weeds, pests, toxin producers, and pathogens that will protect human health. Through New Zealand’s taxonomic knowledge, its natural environment has become associated with recreation and enjoyment. Taxonomic collections of New Zealand have become a cultural heritage that many people value, recognize, protect, and conserve [1]. With this, it is seen that the usage of Taxonomy greatly helps in the advancement of different sectors and greatly aids in the preservation of plant life.

The discovery of new species is done by comparing characteristics shared by different organisms using morphological, behavioral, genetic, and biochemical observations [30]. Besides the use of taxonomy in New Zealand, various places have also used taxonomy in discovering different species. Researchers from the University of the Philippines Los Baños discovered a new critically endangered species in Southern Palawan on July 2019 during their floristic survey. According to [7] Duero (2023), “the researchers saw a bright yellow flowering

treelet belonging to the Proteaceae family, glistening even before the crack of dawn. It was a newly discovered species they named *Helicia danlagunzadii*" (para. 2). In Australia, taxonomists are also able to discover and name many new Australian species every year such as new species of vascular plants, annelids, nematodes, vertebrates, sponges, water bears, bacteria, and many more, that supports the documentation of Australia's rich and diverse biodiversity [15].

Human-made actions have made great impacts on the environment. Looking at the current state of the ecosystem, it is visible that lands and spaces filled with trees and plants before are now high infrastructures and commercial buildings. Global temperatures are continuing to rise and the world is facing a climate crisis. The following is the state of the global climate from 2018-2022:

"The most recent seven years, 2015 to 2021 were the warmest on record. The 2018–2022 global mean temperature average (based on data up to May or June 2022) is estimated to be 1.17 ± 0.13 °C above the 1850–1900 average. A La Niña event has had a slight cooling effect on temperatures in 2021/22 but this will be temporary. Around 90% of the accumulated heat in the Earth's system is stored in the ocean, the Ocean Heat Content for 2018–2022 was higher than in any other 5-year period, with ocean warming rates showing a particularly strong increase in the past two decades." [32]

Blackwell's article on how angiosperms are important in the lives of people stated that flowers are sources of different nutrients as it forms an integral part of food, they also relieve stress and anxiety with their playful and vibrant colors causing instant effects on the mood of people, it also ensures memorable events as it helps a person express his/her own character, and it plays a huge role in the commercial sector for the reason that it can be made into body oils, creams, serums, organic food colorants, and etc, [3]. According to the book [18] Plant Diversity (2016), the common major threats to plants are pollution, climate change, invasive species, fragmentation, habitat loss, and degradation. In addition, the lack of knowledge on how to take care of specific flowering plants also greatly impacts it.

Flowers indeed impact the health of people as stated in the previous paragraph. However, flowers are also an important segment of the tourism industry, greenspaces may be used for different exhibitions, parks, flower festivals, historic, private gardens, and many more [16]. The authors have stated that garden visiting make tourist eager for new experiences that contribute to the memory and identity of the city/nation. In addition to this, "Flora and fauna tourism is advantageous, as it can be indigenous, thus presenting endemic biodiversity and bestowing uniqueness to the destination" [20]. A research showed that the use of fauna and flora as a tourism product greatly boosts the environmental, economic, and political sustainability of a city [17].

Plants that bear fruits and flowers are referred to as flowering plants. According to [14] Morphology of Flowering Plants (2020), "flowering plants are known as angiosperms and they produce seed-bearing fruits" (para.2). These plants reproduce through the process of pollination. The feature that distinguishes them from other plants is their flowers [17].

Guevarra (2022) stated that Baguio City, known as the "City of Pines" is known for its green park spaces and hillsides teeming with gigantic pine trees. Overall, the city is known for its greeneries [8]. According to the [12] City Government of Baguio (2020), the city government will shift from "gray" to "green" as it aims to balance urban development and environmental protection with a comprehensive map and database for the "green spaces" in Baguio city created by the City Planning and Development Office.

Baguio City is the coolest place in the Philippines where the weather and sceneries are fantastic. Aside from the towering pine trees that are seen anywhere in the city, it is also abundant in various fresh flowers that have a splendid charm due to their colors [28]. A variety of plants can be seen anywhere in the city but especially in natural attractions such as the Baguio Botanical Garden, and Burnham Park. The following are the plants that can be seen locally:

- *Helianthus* (sunflower) - an annual herb with a rough hairy stem that belongs to the Aster family or Asteraceae [27]
- *Bellis perennis* (common daisy) - white ray flowers with a yellow disk belonging to the Aster family or Asteraceae [26]
- *Bougainvillea* - inconspicuous flowers belonging to the four-o'clock family or Nyctaginaceae [25]
- *Pachystachys lutea* (golden shrimp plant) - an evergreen shrub that blooms in spring and summer showing its yellow with white accents [13].

To Maschinski, Randall, and Heineman, documentation supports species' survival in the wild. The data that has been carefully collected, disseminated, and documented has tremendous power. It can assist in direct conservation initiatives to conserve more plants if the data is accurate [6]. This could be also the basis for the best plant conservation techniques that can be available globally. Globally, biodiversity is steadily diminishing. Future biodiversity conservation depends on developing accurate information about the identities and geographic distributions of plants by documenting them [29].

Kathryn Williams' (2016) research showed that people often do not care about flowering plants which impacts our efforts to care for and understand plant life due to a human quirk in perception referred to as "Plant Blindness". When an image of an equal number of plants and animals is presented, people remember most of the animals instead of the plants. The same research also showed that generally, people are more interested in animal

life compared to the lives of plants. This biased memory has been termed “Plant Blindness” by Williams. Plant trampling has been a common case, especially in community gardens, populated sidewalks, and streets [31]. Johnson (2017) stated that flowers are the reproductive structure in plants that lead to the formation of seeds and give us fruits. Flowering plants also act as food for other insects and animals and can be used for medical purposes. Truly, flowering plants provide many advantages but botanical education has already been declared under threat [11].

There are many unmindful and ignorant things that humans can do that can put themselves at risk. The more that the awareness deteriorates, the more that the risk increases. The risks that can occur when handling plants incorrectly are blindness, hallucinations, mental disorders/disruptions, dermatitis, severe swelling, drooling, dysphagia, and respiratory compromise [10]. Other symptoms may occur minorly however, the lack of awareness can further increase the recklessness and knowledge to handle plants appropriately. The area of Saint Louis School Inc. has a wide variety of plant life. Most of the students and personnel have little knowledge about the green environment that circulates on the campus. Even more so for the residents of the whole city. The awareness that is aimed to raise with this research paper is focused on the enlightenment of the students, personnel, and residents of Baguio City toward angiosperms and to further the information that is taught to be basic knowledge toward plants to have a better understanding about plants, to learn the care that comes many different ways in terms of the plant health and to also have the courage to spread awareness to people that have lesser knowledge toward the topic [18].

The lack of awareness is what deeply settles this paper. The documentation of these angiosperms provides the necessary information to increase the awareness of each student/personnel and the rest of the Baguio City residents. There have been many cases of deaths and illnesses that have been the cause of the lack of awareness. One case is with the flowering plant called Dump cane/Leopard Lilly or scientifically known as *Dieffenbachia*. It is a relatively benign plant that when handled incorrectly can cause severe discomfort and excruciating swelling of the mouth. One incident happened when one of the relatives of the researchers accidentally ingested the said flower which had been the main cause of his hallucinations and severe brain damage causing him to commit suicide [17]. That is why the researchers have provided this documentation to be able to avoid these kinds of mishaps. This gives massive importance to the awareness of these plants. The students as adolescents can be very reckless with their actions and through this knowledge, the researchers will be able to provide them with the right dos and don'ts when handling plants [9].

The rise of the global climate from 2018-2022 presented above can be addressed with proper plant documentation to preserve the earth's biodiversity. As the city of Baguio will shift from gray to green spaces, the researchers would like to aid in this development by providing documentation on the flowering plants found in Saint Louis School Inc. for there are various plants on the school grounds, but no documentation and study has been conducted. The research will be suggesting ways to preserve and conserve flowering plants that will be of help in addressing the lack of preservation of the biodiversity that has led to the rise of the global climate. Besides this, the study will also be conducted to inform not only students and personnel of the school about the various plants present but also to inform people outside of the school such as the Baguio city government and other organizations.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Research Design*

Qualitative research is defined as the study of nature appropriate for answering questions of why that is observed around the environment and phenomena [4]. Streefkerk (2022), defined quantitative research as research expressed in numbers and graphs and can be quantified mathematically. Conversely, qualitative research is research expressed in words that are used to understand experiences, thoughts, and concepts [21, 22].

- *In Line with this, Bhandari (2022) in her Article on Qualitative Research, Noted the Common Qualitative Methods to Acquire Data:*
- ✓ *Observations: recording what you have seen, heard, or encountered in detailed field notes.*
- ✓ *Interviews: personally asking people questions in one-on-one conversations.*
- ✓ *Focus groups: asking questions and generating discussion among a group of people.*
- ✓ *Surveys: distributing questionnaires with open-ended questions.*
- ✓ *Secondary research: collecting existing data in the form of texts, images, audio or video recordings, etc. (para.6) [2].*

The research on the “Taxonomy of Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.” is under documentative research. According to [19] Scott and Marshall (2015), “Documentary research is often conducted by social scientists to assess a set of documents for historical or social value, or to create a larger narrative through the study of multiple documents surrounding an event or individual” (para. 2). The taxonomy provides a basic understanding of the components of biodiversity which is necessary for effective decision-making about conservation and sustainable use that is why it is needed to be in documentary form. The research is in documentary form for it serves as a record of official information on all flowering plants in Saint Louis School Inc.

➤ *Locale of the Study*

The research was conducted inside the campus of Saint Louis School Inc. The conduction of this research is directed towards the local government, tourists, and residents of Baguio considering that the angiosperms are only accessed by the students and personnel of SLSI. In addition, most of the students of the school are neither aware nor informed in terms of plant life inside the campus. With high hopes for their research, the students would begin to have deeper knowledge about the specifications of the plants around the school, their botanical descriptions, classifications, names, and ways of conservation. The researchers hope that with this knowledge acquired that they will be more mindful of the environment and help in preserving and conserving it.

➤ *Data Gathering Tools*

The tools that we used for data gathering are the following:

- *DSLR Camera,*
- *Notebook,*
- *Ball pen,*
- *Transparent Plastics for plant sample collection,*
- *Interview Questions*

➤ *Data Gathering Procedure*

• *Collection of Plant Images*

The images were collected with the use of a DSLR camera provided by the school. The researchers roamed around the school vicinity to study and take pictures of plant life. These became a part of the documentation process and the source of identification for the flowering plants.

• *Identification of the Plants*

The researchers roamed around the school campus to collect images of different angiosperms which was crucial for classifying each plant's data. The images and plant samples taken were submitted to Mr. Jones T. Napaldet, an associate professor from Benguet State University (BSU) to validate the identification of the plants and provide plant certifications.

• *Classifying Data and Providing Botanical Description*

The researchers were able to gather the information that was used as references to analyze the seen plants which would be able to help them classify the data. In order to validate their findings, the taken images and botanical descriptions were sent to the botanist from Benguet State University (BSU) for an accurate presentation of plant information.

• *Conducting a Frequency Count*

All plant kinds have undergone a frequency count. Dr. Jones T Napaldet from Benguet State University suggested frequency count methods such as plot method and line intercept in order to conduct the count accurately. The researchers have chosen the plot method for the tallying process of each plant kind and plant under the same families.

• *Interviewing of Experts*

A Botanist from the College of Natural Sciences, a faculty member of the College of Agriculture of Benguet State University, and a researcher were interviewed on ways how to preserve and conserve flowering plants. They also gave advice and recommendations to people who are planning to conserve and preserve these angiosperms.

➤ *Treatment of Data*

With the gathered data, frequency count was used to tally the number of occurrences of each flowering plant and plant species under a specific family. Frequency count is the tallying of the number of occurrences of a particular variable, it is used to allow researchers to glance at the data conveniently and identify the most occurring plant species to understand its nature, characteristics, and properties as to why it is the most abundant plant species. In this research, the number of each flowering plant and the plants under a particular family was tallied, and their identifications, classifications, and descriptions were validated by Jones T. Napaldet, an associate professor from Benguet State University.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The outcomes of this research have provided insight into the taxonomy of flowering plants here in the vicinity of Saint Louis School Inc. The researchers have discovered different species of angiosperms surrounding the campus which were identified using the plot system as of March 2023. Each plant is provided with its own scientific name, common name, family, order, genus, species, and botanical description. This chapter provides a reflection on the research process. The input of various interviews of the research paper is discussed, as well as the implications for the interpretation of the results.

➤ *Documentation of Flowering plants*

This table consists of the 16 documented flowering plants growing in the school garden labeled as plot 1. All of the flowering plants in this table fall under the division of Magnoliophyta, with the exception of one flowering plant that belongs to the Liliopsida class which is *Anthurium andraeanum*. In addition, each flowering plant in this table has a different scientific name, common name, family, order, genus, species, and botanical description. This plot has many diverse growing flowering plants because of the wide space and the sunlight it receives due to its location.

Table 1 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. Plot 1 (Garden)

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Aechmea kertesziae</i> Reitz Common Name: Bromeliad Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Family: Bromeliaceae Order: Poales Genus: <i>Aechmea</i> Species: <i>A. kertesziae</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An attractive pot plant or hardy landscape plant, cylindrical spike with rose-red bracts and yellow flowers. A medium-sized clustering plant with an upright rosette shape and short stolons. The green foliage has a dusting of trichomes giving a slight grayish appearance.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Allamanda cathartica</i> L. Common Name: Golden-trumpet Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Allamanda</i> Species: <i>A. cathartica</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An evergreen scandent shrub; branches circular, smooth and green. Leaves in whorls of 4 or opposite, oblong, obovate or oblanceolate, acuminate, cuneate. Inflorescence axillary or a terminal cymose panicle, bracts deciduous. Flower showy, bright yellow. c. 8 cm in diameter; sepals 5, lanceolate-ovate; corolla tube c.2.5 cm long, throat c. 1.25 cm in diameter, lobes orbicular-rotundate c. 3.5 x 4 cm, glabrous; stamens inserted in the throat, acute. Fruit a globose-subglobose prickly capsule; seeds many, obovate, flat winged.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Anthurium andraeanum</i> Linden ex Andre Common Name: Flamingo-lily, Painter’s Palette, Tailflower, Oilcloth flower, Laceleaf Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Anthurium</i> Species: <i>A. andraeanum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: an herbaceous evergreen plant that grows to 40 cm in height. The dark green leaves are heart-shaped and glossy. The inflorescence is made up of cream-yellow low tail-like spadix and waxy red spathe.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Begonia x ricinifolia</i> A.Dietr. Common Name: Castor Bean Begonia Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Begoniaceae Order: Cucurbitales Genus: <i>Begonia</i> Species: <i>B. x ricinifolia</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: It is a vigorous species with huge leaves on hairy fleshy stems arising from a horizontal fleshy rhizome.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Bellis perennis</i> L. Common Name: Daisy Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Asteraceae Order: Asterales Genus: <i>Bellis</i> Species: <i>B. perennis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herbs, perennial or annual, scapose, 10-25 cm tall; scape sparsely villosulous, strigose, sparsely, minutely stipitate-glandular distally (near capitulum). Leaves basal, rosulate, petiole long, winged, blade spatulate, 2-6 × 0.9-2.8 cm, base attenuate, margin serrate to crenate, apex obtuse, sometimes retuse, mucronulate. Capitula terminal, solitary. Ray florets white or pinkish, lamina ca. 10 × 1 mm; disk florets yellow, ca. 2 mm, limb campanulate, ca. 1.5 mm, sparsely hairy proximally, lobes erect, triangular, ca. 0.5 mm, eglandular. Achenes are strigillose. Pappus absent.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Clerodendrum thomsoniae</i> Balf. Common Name: Bleeding– Heart Vine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Lamiaceae Genus: <i>Clerodendrum</i> Species: <i>C. thomsoniae</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Evergreen vine or shrub with a twining growth habit, up to 7 m in length. Smooth, dark green glossy leaves are elliptic with entire leaf margin, measuring up to 15 cm long and 7 cm wide. Leaves are deeply veined and have a long-pointed tip (acuminate apex). Leaf base is obtuse or rounded.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G.Don Common Name: Rose Periwinkle, Bright Eyes, Cape periwinkle, old maid Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Catharanthus</i> Species: <i>C. roseus</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a long-lived (perennial) sub-shrub or herb, usually erect, 30-100 cm high and at least somewhat woody at the base, sometimes sprawling. White latex is present. Stems cylindrical (terete), longitudinally ridged or narrowly winged, green or dark red, pubescent at least when young.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Cuphea hyssopifolia</i> Kunth Common Name: Mexican Heather, Elfin Herb, Hawaiian Heather Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Myrtales Family: Lythraceae Genus: <i>Cuphea</i> Species: <i>C. hyssopifolia</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a rounded, densely branched 1-2' tall tropical sub-shrub. It produces quaint, small, trumpet-shaped flowers with six spreading lavender petals and green calyx tubes.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Dianthus barbatus</i> L. Common Name: Sweet William Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Caryophyllaceae Order: Caryophyllales Genus: <i>Dianthus</i> Species: <i>D. barbatus</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Perennial, up to 70 cm tall. Leaves subtending many flowers in heads. Bracteoles 4-6, ovate with a membranous ciliate margin, apex long acuminate, almost as long as the calyx tube. Calyx 17-23 mm, tubular, teeth lanceolate, acute to acuminate. Petals pink to red or purplish; limb dentate at apex, barbulate.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euryops chrysanthemoides</i> (DC.) B.Nord. Common Name: African Bush Daisy Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Asterales Family: Asteraceae Genus: <i>Euryops</i> Species: <i>E. chrysanthemoides</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: compact densely branched, leafy evergreen shrub growing to a height of 0.5 to 2 metres. The leaves are shaped like those of an oak leaf, with deeply indented lobes and they are close-set, particularly on young growth.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Gardenia jasminoides</i> J.Ellis Common Name: Cape Jasmine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Rubiaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Gardenia</i> Species: <i>G. jasminoides</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Shrubs, 0.3-3 m tall; branches terete to flattened, with buds resinous and distalmost internodes often covered with resin. Leaves opposite or rarely ternate, subsessile to petiolate; blade drying thinly leathery to stiffly papery, oblong-lanceolate, obovate-oblong, obovate, oblanceolate, or elliptic, base cuneate to acute, apex acute to acuminate or obtuse. Flower solitary, terminal; calyx puberulent or pilosulous to glabrous; corolla white to pale yellow, simple; tube 30-50 × 4-6 mm, cylindrical, in throat pilose; lobes (5 or)6(-8) or numerous when doubled, obovate or obovate-oblong, obtuse to rounded. Fruit berry yellow or orange-yellow, ovoid, subglobose, or ellipsoid with persistent calyx lobes to 40 × 6 mm; seeds suborbicular</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hemerocallis citrina</i> Baroni Common Name: Long Yellow Daylily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Asphodelaceae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Hemerocallis</i> Species: <i>H. citrina</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Plants to 1 m tall, deciduous in winter. Roots rather stout, fleshy, usually with oblong, swollen, tuberous part near tip. Leaves linear, 50--130 × 0.5--2.5 cm; leaf sheath with reddish margin. Scape usually slightly longer than leaves, solid; main axis indistinct. Inflorescence branched; helicoidal cymes 3--5 or more, 2--5-flowered; bracts lanceolate, 3--7 cm × 3--6 mm. Pedicel less than 1 cm. Flowers large, fragrant, opening in afternoon or evening and lasting 12--24 hours, purplish black apically in bud. Perianth lemon-colored; tube long, 3--5 cm; segments (6--7)--12 cm, inner ones 2--3 cm wide, slightly wider than outer ones. Filaments 7--8 cm; anthers yellow, 8--10 mm. Capsule ellipsoid</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L. Common Name: Chinese Hibiscus Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Malvales Family: Malvaceae Genus: <i>Hibiscus</i> Species: <i>H. rosa-sinensis</i> Botanical Description: a bushy, evergreen shrub or small tree growing 2.5–5 m (8–16 ft) tall and 1.5–3 m (5–10 ft) wide, with glossy leaves and solitary, brilliant red flowers in summer and autumn. The 5- petaled flowers are 10 cm (4 in) in diameter, with prominent orange-tipped red anthers.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Ixora chinensis</i> Lam. Common Name: West Indian Jasmine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Rubiaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Ixora</i> Species: <i>I. chinensis</i> Botanical Description: Shrub, c. 1 m tall. Leaves subsessile, 6-10 x 3-6 cm, oblong, elliptic, elliptic-obovate, entire, glabrous. Stipules broad, triangular, awned, ± glabrous. Inflorescence of trichotomously branched dense corymbs; bracts small, subulate. Flowers pink, scarlet or orange, central flowers sessile and two side flowers pedicellate, pedicel c. 2.5 mm long, each with a pair of small bracteoles. Calyx-tube c. 1.5 mm long, pubescent; lobes c. 0.5 mm long, tinted red. Corolla-tube 1.5-2 cm long, minutely hairy; lobes elliptic, acute 5-6 mm long. Staminal filaments very short; anthers c. 3 mm long, reflexed. Style exserted, stigma 2-lobed.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pachystachys lutea</i> Nees Common Name: Golden Shrimp Plant Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Acanthaceae Genus: <i>Pachystachys</i> Species: <i>P. lutea</i> Botanical Description: Dark green, lance-shaped, simple leaves, measuring up to 15 cm long, and are oppositely arranged along the stems. The true white flowers are narrow and tubular in shape. Each flower is partly covered by showy and overlapping yellow bracts which make up the 4-sided inflorescence</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pleroma heteromallum</i> (D.Don) D.Don Common Name: silver-leafed princess flower Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Melastomataceae Order: Myrtales Genus: <i>Pleroma</i> Species: <i>P. heteromallum</i> Botanical Description: Shrub, 1.5 – 2 m, moderately covered with appressed, simple or minutely anictrous trichomes, basally inflated or expanded, on the infls' internodes, petioles and rachis. Leaves 7.5 –18 X 4 – 8.5 cm, ovate to elliptic-ovate, 5 –7-veined. fls. with purple petals, with white base (turning red with age), 10–13 X 7–10 mm; stamens ragged, the anthers purple, 4 – 4.5 mm (largest) or ca. 3.5 mm (the smallest)</p>

This table consists of the 10 documented flowering plants present in plot 2 in the school garden. Only one of the flowering plants in this table belongs to a different class, which is Liliopsida. Only two of the flowering plants in this table share a common order, while the others have different orders. They also have different scientific names, common names, families, genera, species, and botanical descriptions. There are fewer documented angiosperms in Plot 2 compared to Plot 1. Aside from the diverse growing flowering plants, this plot is also filled with growing gymnosperms (non-flowering plants).

Table 2 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. Plot 2 (Garden)

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Agapanthus africanus</i> (L.) Hoffmanns. Common Name: African Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Asparagales Family: Amaryllidaceae Genus: <i>Agapanthus</i> Species: <i>A. africanus</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: It is an evergreen species that produces rounded clusters (umbels) of blue, funnel-shaped flowers atop stiff, upright, leafless, fleshy stalks (scapes) typically rising 18-24" tall above a dense mound of basal narrow, strap-shaped, linear, grass-like leaves. Blooms in summer.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Alstroemeria aurea</i> Graham Common Name: Peruvian Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Alstroemericeae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Alstroemeria</i> L. Species: <i>aurea</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: A tuberous perennial native to South America. Terminal clusters of small, lily-like flowers atop slender, upright stems growing in bushy clumps to 2-3' tall. Flowers in yellow or orange, often with spotting and streaking.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Begonia cucullata</i> Willd. Common Name: Wax Flower Begonia Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Begoniaceae Order: Cucurbitales Genus: <i>Begonia</i> Species: <i>B. cucullata</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Stem erect. Petiole glandular; blade basifixed, slightly asymmetric, entire, blade ovate/elliptic; margin serrulate/ciliate/crenate. Flower anther rimose; indumentum tepal(s) glabrous; placenta parted; margin tepal(s) female entire; bracteole(s) flower female present. Fruit capsule wing, strongly non-equal. Seed black numerous, apex obtuse/acute/acuminate.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G.Don Common Name: Rose Periwinkle, Bright Eyes, Cape periwinkle, old maid Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Catharanthus</i> Species: <i>C. roseus</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a long-lived (perennial) sub-shrub or herb, usually erect, 30-100 cm high and at least somewhat woody at the base, sometimes sprawling. White latex is present. Stems cylindrical (terete), longitudinally ridged or narrowly winged, green or dark red, pubescent at least when young.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L. Common Name: Chinese Hibiscus Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Malvales Family: Malvaceae Genus: <i>Hibiscus</i> Species: <i>H. rosa-sinensis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a bushy, evergreen shrub or small tree growing 2.5–5 m (8–16 ft) tall and 1.5–3 m (5–10 ft) wide, with glossy leaves and solitary, brilliant red flowers in summer and autumn. The 5- petaled flowers are 10 cm (4 in) in diameter, with prominent orange-tipped red anthers.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hibiscus syriacus</i> L. Common Name: Rosa of Sharon Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Malvales Family: Malvaceae Genus: <i>Hibiscus</i> Species: <i>H. syriacus</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: hardy deciduous shrub, upright and vase-shaped, reaching 2–4 m (7–13 feet) in height, showy flowers resembling hollyhock blossoms, one leaf per node along the stem, leaf blade length 30-100 mm, leaf blade width 20-40 mm</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Nerium oleander</i> L. Common Name: Rosa Bay Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Nerium</i> Species: <i>N. oleander</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Stem to 6 m tall. Leaves very narrowly elliptic, 5-21 X 1-3.5 cm, leathery, base cuneate or decurrent on petiole, apex acuminate or acute. Flowers showy, fragrant. Sepals narrowly triangular to narrowly ovate, 3-10 mm. Corolla purplish red, pink, white, salmon, or yellow, tube 1.2-2.2 cm; lobes 1.3-3 cm, single or double. Follicles cylindric, 12-23 cm. Seeds oblong, coma 0.9-1.2 cm.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pelargonium inquinans</i> (L.) L'Her. Common Name: scarlet pelargonium Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Geraniaceae Order: Geraniales Genus: <i>Pelargonium</i> L. Species: <i>P. inquinans</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a soft, woody shrub with a height of up to 2 m. The leaves are orbicular with crenate or finely toothed margins and have a velvety feel and glands. The branches of this plant are also velvety and glandular as well as soft when they are young. The branches harden when they become older.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pyrostegia venusta</i> (Ker Gawl.) Miers Common Name: Flame Vine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Bignoniaceae Genus: <i>Pyrostegia</i> Species: <i>P. venusta</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a vigorous, fast-growing, evergreen woody vine that blooms in winter and spring with spectacular reddish-orange flowers. The compound leaves have two or three 2-3 in oval leaflets and are arranged in pairs opposite each other on the stem.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Thunbergia erecta</i> (Benth.) T.Anderson Common Name: Bush Clock Vine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Acanthaceae Order: Lamiales Genus: <i>Thunbergia</i> Species: <i>T. erecta</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Shrub to 3 m tall; younger stems quadrangular, winged, glabrous. Leaves ovate to subrhombic, 5.5 cm x 2.8 cm, attenuate, acute, glabrous, entire to slightly undulate; petioles to ca. 5 mm long, glabrous. Inflorescences axillary, the peduncles borne singly, to 2.3 cm long, glabrous; bracts oblong ovate, 1-2 cm long, 5-8 mm wide, apically acute, basally obtuse, glabrous to minutely puberulous at the apex. Flowers with the calyx reduced to 10-12 teeth ca. 1 mm long; corolla all white or deep violet with a white or yellowish throat, 3 mm wide at the base, the lobes equal, suborbicular, ca. 1.5 cm across, glabrous; cells of the anthers unequal, the base and the margins of the anther cells puberulous.</p>

This table only consists of 1 documented angiosperm which is the flowering plant with the highest frequency count located in the school garden labeled as Plot 3. The flowering plant is from the family of Araceae and belongs to the class of Liliopsida. This flowering plant has the highest frequency count. This may be due to its nature and characteristics. Anthurium andraeanum is considered a houseplant that only requires little care. This flowering plant can also grow despite being in shady places wherein the light is indirect.

Table 3 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. Plot 3 (Garden)

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Anthurium andraeanum</i> Linden ex Andre Common Name: Flamingo-lily, Painter’s Palette, Tailflower, Oilcloth flower, Laceleaf Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Anthurium</i> Species: <i>A. andraeanum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: an herbaceous evergreen plant that grows to 40 cm in height. The dark green leaves are heart-shaped and glossy. The inflorescence is made up of a cream-yellow tail-like spadix and a waxy red spathe.</p>

This table consists of 10 documented flowering plants growing in Plot 4 of the school garden. The ten flowering plants in this table share the same division, and seven of them share a class. Additionally, they all have a unique scientific name, common name, family, order, genus, species, and botanical description. The size of this plot area is smaller compared to Plot 1 and 4. However, despite being small in size, this plot is still filled with diverse angiosperms.

Table 4 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. Plot 4 (Garden)

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Allamanda cathartica</i> L. Common Name: Golden-trumpet Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Allamanda</i> Species: <i>A. cathartica</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An evergreen scandent shrub; branches circular, smooth and green. Leaves in whorls of 4 or opposite, oblong, obovate or oblanceolate, acuminate, cuneate. Inflorescence axillary or a terminal cymose panicle, bracts deciduous. Flower showy, bright yellow. c. 8 cm in diameter; sepals 5, lanceolate-ovate; corolla tube c.2.5 cm long, throat c. 1.25 cm in diameter, lobes orbicular-rotundate c. 3.5 x 4 cm, glabrous; stamens inserted in the throat, acute. Fruit a globose-subglobose prickly capsule; seeds many, obovate, flat winged.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Anthurium andraeanum</i> Linden ex Andre Common Name: Flamingo-lily, Painter’s Palette, Tailflower, Oilcloth flower, Laceleaf Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Anthurium</i> Species: <i>A. andraeanum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: an herbaceous evergreen plant that grows to 40 cm in height. The dark green leaves are heart-shaped and glossy. The inflorescence is made up of a cream-yellow tail-like spadix and a waxy red spathe.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Begonia x ricinifolia</i> A.Dietr. Common Name: Castor Bean Begonia Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Begoniaceae Order: Cucurbitales Genus: <i>Begonia</i> Species: <i>B. x ricinifolia</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: It is a vigorous species with huge leaves on hairy fleshy stems arising from a horizontal fleshy rhizome.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Centaurea jacea</i> L. Common Name: Brown Knapweed Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Asterales Family: Asteraceae Genus: <i>Centaurea</i> Species: <i>C. jacea</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Perennial plant that grows 1-4 ft. (0.3-1.2 m) tall, ridged stems, may have purple stripes, elliptic basal leaves, may become smaller when ascends to stem, flowering occurs from June to October,</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Cuphea hyssopifolia</i> Kunth Common Name: Mexican Heather, Elfin Herb, Hawaiian Heather Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Myrtales Family: Lythraceae Genus: <i>Cuphea</i> Species: <i>C. hyssopifolia</i> Botanical Description: a rounded, densely branched 1-2' tall tropical sub-shrub. It produces quaint, small, trumpet-shaped flowers with six spreading lavender petals and green calyx tubes.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Gomesa flexuosa</i> (G.Lodd.) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams Common Name: Dancing Doll Orchid Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Asparagales Family: Orchidaceae Genus: <i>Gomesa</i> Species: <i>G. flexuosa</i> Botanical Description: Bright yellow 'dancing ladies' featuring brown to dark purple spots, cool to hot growing, carrying 2 apical, spreading, slightly coriaceous, narrowly oblong-ligulate, obtuse or abruptly acute leaves, each branch can rebranch with up to 7 secondary branches, flower size- From 3/4 to 1 1/2 inches [2 to 3 cm]</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Ixora chinensis</i> Lam. Common Name: West Indian Jasmine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Rubiaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Ixora</i> Species: <i>I. chinensis</i> Botanical Description: Shrub, c. 1 m tall. Leaves subsessile, 6-10 x 3-6 cm, oblong, elliptic, elliptic-obovate, entire, glabrous. Stipules broad, triangular, awned, ± glabrous. Inflorescence of trichotomously branched dense corymbs; bracts small, subulate. Flowers pink, scarlet or orange, central flowers sessile and two side flowers pedicellate, pedicel c. 2.5 mm long, each with a pair of small bracteoles. Calyx-tube c. 1.5 mm long, pubescent; lobes c. 0.5 mm long, tinted red. Corolla-tube 1.5-2 cm long, minutely hairy; lobes elliptic, acute 5-6 mm long. Staminal filaments very short; anthers c. 3 mm long, reflexed. Style exserted, stigma 2-lobed.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pachystachys lutea</i> Nees Common Name: Golden Shrimp Plant Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Acanthaceae Genus: <i>Pachystachys</i> Species: <i>P. lutea</i> Botanical Description: Dark green, lance-shaped, simple leaves, measuring up to 15 cm long, and are oppositely arranged along the stems. The true white flowers are narrow and tubular in shape. Each flower is partly covered by showy and overlapping yellow bracts which make up the 4-sided inflorescence</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Rosa transmorrisonensis</i> Hayata Common Name: Glandular rose Division: Magnoliophyta Class: dicotyledons Order: Rosales Family: Rosaceae Genus: <i>Rosa</i> Species: <i>R. transmorrisonensis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Shrubs are evergreen, with branchlets glabrous but with prickles. Stipules mostly adnate to petiole; rachis and petiole pubescent, glandular-pubescent, prickly; leaflets 5–7, rarely 3, elliptic or oblong, 5–25 × 5–15 mm, margin acutely simply serrate, apex rounded-obtuse, acute, or truncate. Flowers solitary or 3–5 in cyme, 1.8–2.5 cm in diam.; pedicel ca. 1.5 cm, glandular-pubescent or not; bracts absent; sepals 5, triangular-ovate, apex acuminate; petals 5, white, obovate, ca. 10 × 5 mm, apex emarginated; styles connate into a column, subequal stamens, villous.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Spathiphyllum wallisii</i> Regel Common Name: Peace Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Spathiphyllum</i> Species: <i>S. wallisii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a herbaceous perennial which produces flowers in the typical aroid structure: a densely crowded inflorescence called a spadix is subtended by one large bract called a spathe (occasionally two spathes are produced, with the upper spathe smaller).</p>

This table consists of the 2 documented flowering plants growing on the plot in front of the school museum. The flowering plants in this table share a class and division but have unique scientific names, common names, family names, orders, genera, species, and botanical descriptions. The size of this plot area is only small and does not receive much sunlight compared to the plot areas located in the school garden.

Table 5 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. Old Prayer Room

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Dianthus barbatus</i> L. Common Name: Sweet William Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Caryophyllaceae Order: Caryophyllales Genus: <i>Dianthus</i> Species: <i>D. barbatus</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Perennial, up to 70 cm tall. Leaves subtending many flowers in heads. Bracteoles 4-6, ovate with a membranous ciliate margin, apex long acuminate, almost as long as the calyx tube. Calyx 17-23 mm, tubular, teeth lanceolate, acute to acuminate. Petals pink to red or purplish; limb dentate at apex, barbate.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Allamanda schottii</i> Pohl Common Name: Bush Allamanda Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Gentianales Family: Apocynaceae Genus: <i>Allamanda</i> L Species: <i>A. schottii</i>.</p> <p>Botanical Description: It is a tropical and evergreen shrub, which can grow up to 1.5 m tall. Leaves are leathery, elliptical to obovate shape, whorled along the stem, leaf blade is green and lined with greyish margin. Clusters of yellow, trumpet-shaped with orange throat, and the fused corolla is stripy.</p>
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The table consists of the 3 documented flowering plants that do not belong to any of the plots in the school garden. The documented flowering plants belonging in this table share the same class. These flowering plants are frequently being moved around the school vicinity because they are placed in clay pots.

Table 6 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. (More documented potted plants at the Garden)

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> Willd. Common Name: Brazil Bougainvillea Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Nyctaginaceae Order: Caryophyllales Genus: <i>Bougainvillea</i> Species: <i>B. spectabilis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: grows as a woody vine or shrub, reaching 15 to 40 feet (4.6 to 12.2 m) with heart-shaped leaves and thorny, pubescent stems. The flowers are generally small, white, and inconspicuous, highlighted by several brightly colored modified leaves called bracts.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pelargonium x hybridum</i> (L.) L’Her. Common Name: Zonal Geranium Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Dicotyledons Family: Geraniaceae Order: Geraniales Genus: <i>Geraniums</i> Species: <i>x hybridum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Tender perennials with somewhat brittle, trailing stems that spread to as much as 3' wide. They feature thick, lobed, medium green, ivy-like leaves and clusters of single or double flowers in shades of red, pink, lilac, or white.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Petunia x atkinsiana</i> (Sweet) D.Don ex W.H.Baxter Common Name: Common Garden Petunia Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Solanaceae Order: Solanales Genus: <i>Petunia</i> Species: <i>P. x atkinsiana</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herbs annual, 30-60 cm tall, glandular-hairy. Leaves short petiolate or subsessile; leaf blade ovate, 3-8 × 1.5-4.5 cm, base cuneate, margin entire, apex acute. Pedicel 3-5 cm. Calyx deeply parted, 1-1.8 cm × 3.5 mm; lobes linear, 1-1.5 cm × 3.5 mm, obtuse. Corolla white, red, yellow, or purple, sometimes fragrant, funnellform, 5-7 cm, limb spreading. Style slightly exceeding stamens. Capsules conical, ca. 1 cm. Seeds subglobose, ca. 0.5 mm in diam.</p>

The table consists of 5 documented flowering plants in the grotto near the school’s faculty room. The flowering plants documented share the same division, 2 plants have a different class. But every flowering plant has a different scientific and common name, family, order, genus, species, and botanical description. The plot of flowering plants receives a lot of sunlight and is always being seen by students and teachers who pass by.

Table 7 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.-Grotto Near the Faculty Room.

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Cuphea hyssopifolia</i> Kunth Common Name: Mexican Heather, Elfin Herb, Hawaiian Heather Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Myrtales Family: Lythraceae Genus: <i>Cuphea</i> Species: <i>C. hyssopifolia</i> Botanical Description: a rounded, densely branched 1-2' tall tropical sub-shrub. It produces quaint, small, trumpet-shaped flowers with six spreading lavender petals and green calyx tubes.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Ipomoea cairica</i> (L.) Sweet Common Name: Messina Creeper Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Convolvulaceae Order: Solanales Genus: <i>Ipomoea</i> Species: <i>I. cairica</i> Botanical Description: Herbs perennial, twining, with a tuberous root; axial parts glabrous. Stems to 5 m, thinly angular, ± tuberculate or smooth. Petiole 2-8 cm, base with leafy pseudostipules; leaf blade palmately 5-parted to base; lobes entire or minutely undulate, apex acute or obtuse. Inflorescences 1- or several flowered; peduncle 2-8 cm. Pedicel 0.5-2 cm, sometimes verruculose. Sepals unequal; outer 2 sepals 4-6.5 mm; inner ones 5-9 mm, glabrous. Corolla pink, purple, or reddish purple, with a darker center, rarely white, funnellform. Stamens included, unequal. Ovary is glabrous. Stigma 2-lobed. Capsule ± globose, ca. 1 cm. Seeds black, ca. 5 mm, densely tomentose, margin with longer hairs</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pachystachys lutea</i> Nees Common Name: Golden Shrimp Plant Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Acanthaceae Genus: <i>Pachystachys</i> Species: <i>P. lutea</i> Botanical Description: Dark green, lance-shaped, simple leaves, measuring up to 15 cm long, and are oppositely arranged along the stems. The true white flowers are narrow and tubular in shape. Each flower is partly covered by showy and overlapping yellow bracts which make up the 4-sided inflorescence</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pelargonium x hybridum</i> (L.) L’Her. Common Name: Zonal Geranium Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Dicotyledons Family: Geraniaceae Order: Geraniales Genus: <i>Geraniums</i> Species: <i>x hybridum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Tender perennials with somewhat brittle, trailing stems that spread to as much as 3' wide. They feature thick, lobed, medium green, ivy-like leaves and clusters of single or double flowers in shades of red, pink, lilac, or white.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Spathiphyllum wallisii</i> Regel Common Name: Peace Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Spathiphyllum</i> Species: <i>S. wallisii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An herbaceous perennial that produces flowers in the typical aroid structure: a densely crowded inflorescence called a spadix is subtended by one large bract called a spathe (occasionally two spathes are produced, with the upper spathe smaller).</p>

The table consists of 13 documented flowering plants in the grotto near the playground. The 12 documented flowering plants share the same division. One plant has a different division. In addition to this, all flowering plants have different scientific and common names, classes, families, orders, genera, species, and botanical descriptions. The plot area is what students, teachers, and visitors often see when visiting and walking by the school vicinity. This plant area has the highest number of plant species belonging to different plant families. This location receives direct sunlight and is also filled with various gymnosperms.

Table 8 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.-Grotto near the Playground

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Aechmea kertesziae</i> Reitz Common Name: Bromeliad Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Family: Bromeliaceae Order: Poales Genus: <i>Aechmea</i> Species: <i>A. kertesziae</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An attractive pot plant or hardy landscape plant, cylindrical spike with rose-red bracts and yellow flowers. A medium-sized clustering plant with an upright rosette shape and short stolons. The green foliage has a dusting of trichomes giving a slight grayish appearance.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Allamanda cathartica</i> L. Common Name: Golden-trumpet Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Allamanda</i> Species: <i>A. cathartica</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An evergreen scandent shrub; branches circular, smooth and green. Leaves in whorls of 4 or opposite, oblong, obovate or oblanceolate, acuminate, cuneate. Inflorescence axillary or a terminal cymose panicle, bracts deciduous. Flower showy, bright yellow. c. 8 cm in diameter; sepals 5, lanceolate-ovate; corolla tube c.2.5 cm long, throat c.</p>

	<p>1.25 cm in diameter, lobes orbicular-rotundate c. 3.5 x 4 cm, glabrous; stamens inserted in the throat, acute. Fruit a globose-subglobose prickly capsule; seeds many, obovate, flat winged.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Alstroemeria aurea</i> Graham Common Name: Peruvian Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Alstroemericeae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Alstroemeria</i> L. Species: <i>aurea</i> Botanical Description: A tuberous perennial native to South America. Terminal clusters of small, lily-like flowers top slender, upright stems growing in bushy clumps to 2-3' tall. Flowers in yellow or orange, often with spotting and streaking.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Anthurium andraeanum</i> Linden ex Andre Common Name: Flamingo-lily, Painter's Palette, Tailflower, Oilcloth flower, Laceleaf Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Anthurium</i> Species: <i>A. andraeanum</i> Botanical Description: herbaceous evergreen plant that grows to 40 cm in height. The dark green leaves are heart-shaped and glossy. The inflorescence is made up of a cream yellow tail-like spadix and waxy red spathe.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G.Don Common Name: Rose Periwinkle, Bright Eyes, Cape periwinkle, old maid Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Apocynaceae Order: Gentianales Genus: <i>Catharanthus</i> Species: <i>C. roseus</i> Botanical Description: a long-lived (perennial) sub-shrub or herb, usually erect, 30-100 cm high, and at least somewhat woody at the base, sometimes sprawling. White latex is present. Stems cylindrical (terete), longitudinally ridged or narrowly winged, green or dark red, pubescent at least when young.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Epidendrum radicans</i> Pav. ex Lindl. Common Name: Fire-star Orchid Division: Tracheophyta Class: Monocotyledonae Family: Orchidaceae Order: Orchidales Genus: <i>Epidendrum</i> Species: <i>E. radicans</i> Botanical Description: Erect to creeping herbs. Roots white, few from stem bases. Stems reedlike, sometimes branched, terete to 50 cm long, covered by persistent leaf sheaths. Leaves numerous, distichous; sheaths tightly clasping stem; blades rigid, fleshy-coriaceous, elliptic-lanceolate, obtuse to rounded, 4-7 x 1.7-2.4 cm. Inflorescence peduncle covered by scarious sheaths, 30-50 cm long, raceme congested, many-flowered, flowers opening in succession and floral displays sub umbellate. Flowers are bicolorred, non-resupinate, and odorless. Sepals and petals red-orange, spreading. Fruits green, pendent; pedicel 10-12 mm long; ovary ellipsoidal; beak 17-22 mm long.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euryops chrysanthemoides</i> (DC.) B.Nord. Common Name: African Bush Daisy Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Asterales Family: Asteraceae Genus: <i>Euryops</i> Species: <i>E. chrysanthemoides</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: compact densely branched, leafy evergreen shrub growing to a height of 0.5 to 2 metres. The leaves are shaped like those of an oak leaf, with deeply indented lobes and they are close-set, particularly on young growth.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hemerocallis citrina</i> Baroni Common Name: Long Yellow Daylily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Asphodelaceae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Hemerocallis</i> Species: <i>H. citrina</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Plants up to 1 m tall, deciduous in winter. Roots are rather stout, and fleshy, usually with oblong, swollen, tuberous parts near the tip. Leaves linear, 50--130 × 0.5--2.5 cm; leaf sheath with reddish margin. Scape is usually slightly longer than leaves, solid; the main axis indistinct. Inflorescence branched; helicoidal cymes 3--5 or more, 2--5-flowered; bracts lanceolate, 3--7 cm × 3--6 mm. Pedicel less than 1 cm. Flowers large, fragrant, opening in the afternoon or evening and lasting 12--24 hours, purplish black apically in the bud. Perianth lemon-colored; tube long, 3--5 cm; segments (6--7)--12 cm, inner ones 2--3 cm wide, slightly wider than outer ones. Filaments 7--8 cm; anthers yellow, 8--10 mm. Capsule ellipsoid.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hippeastrum reginae</i> (L.) Herb. Common Name: Amaryllis Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Family: Amaryllidaceae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Hippeastrum</i> Species: <i>H. reginae</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herb: bulb subterranean. Leaf linear flat, apex obtuse. Inflorescence 2 - 4. Flower perigonium infundibular, apex red dark/orange, base white yellowish, tube 2.5 - 6 cm long; sepal wider than the petal, elliptic; petal elliptic, lower slightly smaller than the upper/equal the upper; corona fimbriate free/fimbriate partly adnate connate; filament fasciculate/smaller than long of the sepal and petal; colour of the anther yellow or cream; stigma capitate globose/capitate with lobe(s) triangular. Fruit: capsule brown internally; seed numerous, discoid flattened.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hippeastrum reticulatum</i> (L'Her.) Herb. Common Name: Stripe-leaf Amaryllis Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Family: Amaryllidaceae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Hippeastrum</i> Species: <i>H. reticulatum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herb, bulb subterranean. Leaf lanceolate pseudo petiolate; apex of the leaf acute. Inflorescence 5 to 8. Flower perigonium infundibular; apex white/pinkish/tessellate of the pink dark; base white/in-furrow median; tube 2.5 - 6 cm; sepal slightly wider than the petal, elliptic; petal lower slightly smaller than the upper; corona absent; filament fasciculate/very smaller than long of the sepal and petal; the color of the anther purple or atropurpureus; stigma capitate globose. Fruit reed capsule; seed numerous, globose</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pachystachys lutea</i> Nees Common Name: Golden Shrimp Plant Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Acanthaceae Genus: <i>Pachystachys</i> Species: <i>P. lutea</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Dark green, lance-shaped, simple leaves, measuring up to 15 cm long, and are oppositely arranged along the stems. The true white flowers are narrow and tubular in shape. Each flower is partly covered by showy and overlapping yellow bracts which make up the 4-sided inflorescence</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Rosa transmorrisonensis</i> Hayata Common Name: Glandular rose Division: Magnoliophyta Class: dicotyledons Order: Rosales Family: Rosaceae Genus: <i>Rosa</i> Species: <i>R. transmorrisonensis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Shrubs evergreen, branchlets glabrous but with prickles. Stipules mostly adnate to petiole; rachis and petiole pubescent, glandular-pubescent, prickly; leaflets 5–7, rarely 3, elliptic or oblong, 5–25 × 5–15 mm, margin acutely simply serrate, apex rounded-obtuse, acute, or truncate. Flowers solitary or 3–5 in cyme, 1.8–2.5 cm in diam.; pedicel ca. 1.5 cm, glandular-pubescent or not; bracts absent; sepals 5, triangular-ovate, apex acuminate; petals 5, white, obovate, ca. 10 × 5 mm, apex emarginated; styles connate into column, subequaling stamens, villous.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Spathiphyllum wallisii</i> Regel Common Name: Peace Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Spathiphyllum</i> Species: <i>S. wallisii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: An herbaceous perennial which produces flowers in the typical aroid structure: a densely crowded inflorescence called a spadix is subtended by one large bract called a spathe (occasionally two spathes are produced, with the upper spathe smaller).</p>

The table consists of 11 documented flowering plants near the old guidance office of Saint Louis School Inc. The 10 documented flowering plants share the same division, one plant has a different class and another plant has a different class and division. Every flowering plant has a different scientific and common name, family, order, genus, species, and botanical description. This plant area is wide in size and filled with many spaces to grow more flowering plants. Parts of this area receive direct light. However, some only receive indirect light and are growing in shady spots.

Table 9 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.-Old Guidance Office

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Allamanda schottii</i> Pohl Common Name: Bush Allamanda Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Gentianales Family: Apocynaceae Genus: <i>Allamanda</i> L Species: <i>A. schottii</i>.</p> <p>Botanical Description: It is a tropical and evergreen shrub, which can grow to 1.5 m tall. Leaves are leathery, elliptical to obovate shape, whorled along the stem, leaf blade is green and lined with greyish margin. Clusters of yellow, trumpet-shaped with orange throat and the fused corolla is stripy.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Alstroemeria aurea</i> Graham Common Name: Peruvian Lily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Alstroemericeae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Alstroemeria</i> L. Species: <i>aurea</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: A tuberous perennial native to South America. Terminal clusters of small, lily-like flowers top slender, upright stems growing in bushy clumps to 2-3' tall. Flowers in yellow or orange, often with spotting and streaking.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Anthurium andraeanum</i> Linden ex Andre Common Name: Flamingo-lily, Painter's Palette, Tailflower, Oilcloth flower, Laceleaf Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Order: Alismatales Family: Araceae Genus: <i>Anthurium</i> Species: <i>A. andraeanum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: herbaceous evergreen plant that grows to 40 cm in height. The dark green leaves are heart-shaped and glossy. The inflorescence is made up of a cream yellow tail-like spadix and waxy red spathe.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> Willd. Common Name: Brazil Bougainvillea Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Nyctaginaceae Order: Caryophyllales Genus: <i>Bougainvillea</i> Species: <i>B. spectabilis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: grows as a woody vine or shrub, reaching 15 to 40 feet (4.6 to 12.2 m) with heart-shaped leaves and thorny, pubescent stems. The flowers are generally small, white, and inconspicuous, highlighted by several brightly colored modified leaves called bracts.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euryops chrysanthemoides</i> (DC.) B.Nord. Common Name: African Bush Daisy Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Asterales Family: Asteraceae Genus: <i>Euryops</i> Species: <i>E. chrysanthemoides</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: compact densely branched, leafy evergreen shrub growing to a height of 0.5 to 2 metres. The leaves are shaped like those of an oak leaf, with deeply indented lobes and they are close-set, particularly on young growth.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Duranta erecta</i> L. Common Name: Golden Dewdrop Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Verbenaceae Order: Lamiales Genus: <i>Duranta</i> Species: <i>D. erecta</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Large, evergreen shrub with multiple stems and hanging branches that have a sprawling growth habit. Leaves are ovate with serrate to the entire leaf margin (2.5 – 7.5 cm long). Light purple, tubular flowers are 5-lobed (1.3 cm wide).</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Epidendrum radicans</i> Pav. ex Lindl. Common Name: Fire-star Orchid Division: Tracheophyta Class: Monocotyledonae Family: Orchidaceae Order: Orchidales Genus: <i>Epidendrum</i> Species: <i>E. radicans</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Erect to creeping herbs. Roots white, few from stem bases. Stems reedlike, sometimes branched, terete to 50 cm long, covered by persistent leaf sheaths. Leaves numerous, distichous; sheaths tightly clasping stem; blades rigid, fleshy-coriaceous, elliptic-lanceolate, obtuse to rounded, 4-7 x 1.7-2.4 cm. Inflorescence peduncle covered by scarious sheaths, 30-50 cm long, raceme congested, many-flowered, flowers opening in succession and floral displays sub umbellate. Flowers are bicolorred, non-resupinate, and odorless. Sepals and petals red-orange, spreading. Fruits green, pendent; pedicel 10-12 mm long; ovary ellipsoidal; beak 17-22 mm long.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Erigeron sumatrensis</i> Retz. Common Name: Fleabane Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Asteraceae Order: Asterales Genus: <i>Erigeron</i> Species: <i>E. sumatrensis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herbs, annual or biennial, 80-150 cm tall, stems erect, thick. Leaves: basal withered at anthesis, lower cauline petiolate, blade oblanceolate or lanceolate; mid and upper reduced, blade narrowly lanceolate to linear, margin serrate or entire. Capitula 5-8 mm in diam., numerous, in large and long paniculiform synflorescences. Involucre campanulate to urceolate, gray-green. Ray florets numerous, 4-4.5 mm, lamina yellowish or purplish, short, filiform, apex 2-denticulate; disk florets 6-11, yellowish, ca. 4 mm, tube sparsely puberulent. Achenes linear-lanceoloid, compressed; pappus white, later yellowish brown.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hemerocallis citrina</i> Baroni Common Name: Long Yellow Daylily Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Asphodelaceae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Hemerocallis</i> Species: <i>H. citrina</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Plants to 1 m tall, deciduous in winter. Roots rather stout, fleshy, usually with oblong, swollen, tuberous part near tip. Leaves linear, 50--130 × 0.5--2.5 cm; leaf sheath with reddish margin. Scape usually slightly longer than leaves, solid; main axis indistinct. Inflorescence branched; helicoidal cymes 3--5 or more, 2--5-flowered; bracts lanceolate, 3--7 cm × 3--6 mm. Pedicel less than 1 cm. Flowers large, fragrant, opening in afternoon or evening and lasting 12--24 hours, purplish black apically in bud. Perianth lemon-colored; tube long, 3--5 cm; segments (6--7)--12 cm, inner ones 2--3 cm wide, slightly wider than outer ones. Filaments 7--8 cm; anthers yellow, 8--10 mm. Capsule ellipsoid</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pachystachys lutea</i> Nees Common Name: Golden Shrimp Plant Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Acanthaceae Genus: <i>Pachystachys</i> Species: <i>P. lutea</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Dark green, lance-shaped, simple leaves, measuring up to 15 cm long, and are oppositely arranged along the stems. The true white flowers are narrow and tubular in shape. Each flower is partly covered by showy and overlapping yellow bracts which make up the 4-sided inflorescence.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Rhododendron indicum</i> (L.) Sweet Common Name: Macranthum Azalea Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Ericaceae Order: Ericales Genus: <i>Rhododendron</i> Species: <i>R. indicum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Shrubs, semi evergreen, 1--2 m tall; branches many; young shoots densely red-brown strigose, glabrescent. Petiole 2--4 mm, coarsely red-brown strigose; leaf blade papery, narrowly lanceolate or oblanceolate; base narrowly cuneate; margin sparsely and finely crenate-serrate; apex obtusely pointed. Inflorescence 1--3-flowered; corolla broadly funnellform, bright red, occasionally rose-red, with dark red flecks, 3--4 × 3.7(–6) cm; stamens 5, unequal, 1.6--2.2 cm, shorter than corolla, filaments puberulent at base; ovary ca. 3 mm, densely shiny brown strigose; style 2.3(–4.5) cm, longer than stamens, glabrous. Capsule oblong-ovoid, 6--8 mm, densely red-brown strigose.</p>

The table consists of 6 documented flowering plants in the school playground that are placed in pots that are frequently moved around. All 6 flowering plants documented share the same division, one has a different class. Every plant has a different scientific and common name, family, order, genus, species, and botanical description. These plants are frequently being moved around. Thus, their location is not constant and may be placed in different plant areas.

Table 10 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.-Potted Plants in the Playground

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> Willd. Common Name: Brazil Bougainvillea Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Nyctaginaceae Order: Caryophyllales Genus: <i>Bougainvillea</i> Species: <i>B. spectabilis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: grows as a woody vine or shrub, reaching 15 to 40 feet (4.6 to 12.2 m) with heart-shaped leaves and thorny, pubescent stems. The flowers are generally small, white, and inconspicuous, highlighted by several brightly colored modified leaves called bracts.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Clerodendrum thomsoniae</i> Balf. Common Name: Bleeding– Heart Vine Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Lamiaceae Genus: <i>Clerodendrum</i> Species: <i>C. thomsoniae</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Evergreen vine or shrub with a twining growth habit, up to 7 m in length. Smooth, dark green glossy leaves are elliptic with entire leaf margin, measuring up to 15 cm long and 7 cm wide. Leaves are deeply veined and have a long-pointed tip (acuminate apex). Leaf base is obtuse or rounded.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euphorbia milii</i> Des Moul. Common Name: Crown of Thorns Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Dicotyledons Family: Euphorbiaceae Order: Malpighiales Genus: <i>Euphorbia</i> Species: <i>E. milii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Erect shrub, succulent, spiny, terete, bark brown to greyish; younger branches ca 8 mm in diam. Spines in spirals or in indistinct rows not on spineshields, solitary or in groups of 3 or more 16–25 mm long, grey to brown. Glabrous. Leaves sessile; blade obovate elliptic, ca 1.5–5 by 0.8–2 cm, base attenuate, margin entire, apex obtuse-mucronate; venation hardly visible. Cyathia several in exserted dichasia with long peduncles; bracts at branching 2 mm long, membranous, inconspicuous; bracts below cyathia in pairs, red or yellow or white or in various colours, showy and petaloid, 1–2 cm long; cyathia sessile in bracts, glands 4, without appendages. Fruits and seeds not seen, the seeds described or 3–4 mm long, brownish.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euryops chrysanthemoides</i> (DC.) B.Nord. Common Name: African Bush Daisy Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Asterales Family: Asteraceae Genus: <i>Euryops</i> Species: <i>E. chrysanthemoides</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: compact densely branched, leafy evergreen shrub growing to a height of 0.5 to 2 metres. The leaves are shaped like those of an oak leaf, with deeply indented lobes and they are close-set, particularly on young growth.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Kalanchoe pinnata</i> (Lam.) Pers. Common Name: Cathedral Bells Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Saxifragales Family: Crassulaceae Genus: <i>Kalanchoe</i> Species: <i>K. pinnata</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herbaceous succulent shrub, up to 1.8m height. Leaves smooth, glossy, fleshy, with brownish crenate margins, from which plant produces new plantlets. Lower leaves simple, upper leaves compound with 3-7 leaflets held on long petioles.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Petunia x atkinsiana</i> (Sweet) D. Don ex W.H. Baxter Common Name: Common Garden Petunia Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Solanaceae Order: Solanales Genus: <i>Petunia</i> Species: <i>P. x atkinsiana</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herbs annual, 30-60 cm tall, glandular hairy. Leaves short petiolate or subsessile; leaf blade ovate, 3-8 × 1.5-4.5 cm, base cuneate, margin entire, apex acute. Pedicel 3-5 cm. Calyx deeply parted, 1-1.8 cm × 3.5 mm; lobes linear, 1-1.5 cm × 3.5 mm, obtuse. Corolla white, red, yellow, or purple, sometimes fragrant, funnellform, 5-7 cm, limb spreading. Style slightly exceeding stamens. Capsules conical, ca. 1 cm. Seeds subglobose, ca. 0.5 mm in diam.</p>

This table consist of the 3 documented flowering plants located at the driveway by the back of the school. In this table, 3 flowering plants have the same division which is Magnoliophyta. In addition to this, the flowering plants have different scientific names, common names, classes, families, orders, genus, species, and botanical descriptions. This area only consists of a small number of angiosperms. All of the flowering plants in this area are potted, meaning, they can easily be moved around.

Table 11 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.-Driveway on Back of School

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Clerodendrum schmidtii</i> C.B Clarke Common Name: Chains Of Glory Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Lamiaceae (Formerly: Verbenaceae) Order: Lamiales Genus: <i>Clerodendrum</i> Species: <i>C. schmidtii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a shrub to small tree, multi-stemmed, with a weeping habit. Each winter it grows long, pendent, dark red racemes, eighteen inches long, which fill with delicate white flowers.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euphorbia milii</i> Des Moul. Common Name: Crown of Thorns Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Dicotyledons Family: Euphorbiaceae Order: Malpighiales Genus: <i>Euphorbia</i> Species: <i>E. milii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Erect shrub, succulent, spiny, terete, bark brown to greyish; younger branches ca 8 mm in diam. Spines in spirals or in indistinct rows not on spineshields, solitary or in groups of 3 or more 16-25 mm long, grey to brown. Glabrous. Leaves subsessile; blade obovate elliptic, ca 1.5-5 by 0.8-2 cm, base attenuate, margin entire, apex obtuse-mucronate; venation hardly visible. Cyathia several in exserted dichasia with long peduncles; bracts at</p>

	<p>branching 2 mm long, membranous, inconspicuous; bracts below cyathia in pairs, red or yellow or white or in various colours, showy and petaloid, 1–2 cm long; cyathia sessile in bracts, glands 4, without appendages. Fruits and seeds not seen, the seeds described or 3–4 mm long, brownish.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L. Common Name: Chinese Hibiscus Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Malvales Family: Malvaceae Genus: <i>Hibiscus</i> Species: <i>H. rosa-sinensis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a bushy, evergreen shrub or small tree growing 2.5–5 m (8–16 ft) tall and 1.5–3 m (5–10 ft) wide, with glossy leaves and solitary, brilliant red flowers in summer and autumn. The 5- petaled flowers are 10 cm (4 in) in diameter, with prominent orange-tipped red anthers.</p>

This table consists of the 7 documented flowering plants located in the back of the school area which is often closed to students. In this table, all flowering plants belong under the division which is Magnoliophyta and have different scientific names, common names, classes, families, orders, genus, species, and botanical descriptions. This area does not consist of many flowering plants, rather, more gymnosperms or non-flowering plants.

Table 12 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc.-Back of the School

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> Willd. Common Name: Brazil Bougainvillea Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Nyctaginaceae Order: Caryophyllales Genus: <i>Bougainvillea</i> Species: <i>B. spectabilis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: grows as a woody vine or shrub, reaching 15 to 40 feet (4.6 to 12.2 m) with heart-shaped leaves and thorny, pubescent stems. The flowers are generally small, white, and inconspicuous, highlighted by several brightly colored modified leaves called bracts.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Cuphea hyssopifolia</i> Kunth Common Name: Mexican Heather, Elfin Herb, Hawaiian Heather Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Myrtales Family: Lythraceae Genus: <i>Cuphea</i> Species: <i>C. hyssopifolia</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: a rounded, densely branched 1-2' tall tropical sub-shrub. It produces quaint, small, trumpet-shaped flowers with six spreading lavender petals and green calyx tubes.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Euphorbia milii</i> Des Moul. Common Name: Crown of Thorns Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Dicotyledons Family: Euphorbiaceae Order: Malpighiales Genus: <i>Euphorbia</i> Species: <i>E. milii</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Erect shrub, succulent, spiny, terete, bark brown to greyish; younger branches ca 8 mm in diam. Spines in spirals or in indistinct rows not on spineshields, solitary or in groups of 3 or more 16–25 mm long, grey to brown. Glabrous. Leaves subsessile; blade obovate elliptic, ca 1.5–5 by 0.8–2 cm, base attenuate, margin entire, apex obtuse-mucronate; venation hardly visible. Cyathia several in exserted dichasia with long peduncles; bracts at branching 2 mm long, membranous, inconspicuous; bracts below cyathia in pairs, red or yellow or white or in various colours, showy and petaloid, 1–2 cm long; cyathia sessile in bracts, glands 4, without appendages. Fruits and seeds not seen, the seeds described or 3–4 mm long, brownish.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Hippeastrum reticulatum</i> (L’Her.) Herb. Common Name: Stripe-leaf Amaryllis Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Liliopsida Family: Amaryllidaceae Order: Asparagales Genus: <i>Hippeastrum</i> Species: <i>H. reticulatum</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herb, bulb subterranean. Leaf lanceolate pseudo petiolate; apex of the leaf acute. Inflorescence 5 to 8. Flower perigonium infundibular; apex white/pinkish/tessellate of the pink dark; base white/in furrow median; tube 2.5 - 6 cm; sepal slightly wider the petal, elliptic; petal lower slightly smaller than the upper; corona absent; filament fasciculate/very smaller than long of the sepal and petal; colour of the anther purple or atropurpureus; stigma capitate globose. Fruit reed capsule; seed numerous, globose.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> Mill. Common Name: Spike Lavender Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Lamiaceae Genus: <i>Lavandula</i> Species: <i>L. angustifolia</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: This is a semi-woody plant that typically grows to 1.5-3'. Narrow, gray-green leaves (to 2 1/2" long) on square stems. Purple flowers appear in terminal spikes in late spring to early summer. Both foliage and flowers are highly aromatic.</p>
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Pachystachys lutea</i> Nees Common Name: Golden Shrimp Plant Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Acanthaceae Genus: <i>Pachystachys</i> Species: <i>P. lutea</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Dark green, lance-shaped, simple leaves, measuring up to 15 cm long, and are oppositely arranged along the stems. The true white flowers are narrow and tubular in shape. Each flower is partly covered by showy and overlapping yellow bracts which make up the 4-sided inflorescence.</p>

	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Tecoma capensis</i> (Thunb.) Lindl. Common Name: Cape Honeysuckle Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales Family: Bignoniaceae Genus: <i>Tecoma</i> Species: <i>T. capensis</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Evergreen shrub with a scrambling growth habit or long vine when provided mechanical support (up to 6 - 9 m long). Shiny green leaves are pinnately compound (15 cm long). They are composed of 5 - 7 toothed leaflets (5 cm long) that lack stalks and occur in pairs.</p>
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This table consists of the only documented plant located in the school quadrangle. Presented in this table is the only flowering plant that is located on the school quadrangle. All of these flowering plants are potted for it to be easier to move by school personnel. These *Petunia x Atkinsiana* plants provide a more colorful view of the overall sight of the quadrangle.

Table 13 Flowering Plants in Saint Louis School Inc. – School quadrangle

Plant Image:	Description:
	<p>Scientific Name: <i>Petunia x atkinsiana</i> (Sweet) D.Don ex W.H.Baxter Common Name: Common Garden Petunia Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Family: Solanaceae Order: Solanales Genus: <i>Petunia</i> Species: <i>P. x atkinsiana</i></p> <p>Botanical Description: Herbs annual, 30-60 cm tall, glandular-hairy. Leaves short petiolate or sessile; leaf blade ovate, 3-8 × 1.5-4.5 cm, base cuneate, margin entire, apex acute. Pedicel 3-5 cm. Calyx deeply parted, 1-1.8 cm × 3.5 mm; lobes linear, 1-1.5 cm × 3.5 mm, obtuse. Corolla white, red, yellow, or purple, sometimes fragrant, funnellform, 5-7 cm, limb spreading. Style slightly exceeding stamens. Capsules conical, ca. 1 cm. Seeds subglobose, ca. 0.5 mm in diameter.</p>

➤ *Frequency Count of Flowering Plants*

This table shows the frequency of each flowering plant species. The plot method has been used for easier tallying of each species.

Table 14 Angiosperm Frequency Count

Plant Name	Frequency
Aechmea kertesziae	3
Agapanthus africanus	3
Allamanda schotti	2
Allamanda cathartica	6
Alstroemeria hybrids	9
Anthurium andraeanum	96
Begonia cucullata	1
Begonia x ricinifolia	2
Bellis perennis	1

<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i>	21
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	17
<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	3
<i>Clerodendrum schmidtii</i>	4
<i>Clerodendrum thomsoniae</i>	8
<i>Cuphea hyssopifolia</i>	12
<i>Dianthus barbatus</i>	4
<i>Duranta erecta</i>	4
<i>Epidendrum radicans</i>	4
<i>Erigeron sumatrensis</i>	1
<i>Euphorbia milii</i>	13
<i>Euryops chrysanthemoides</i>	8
<i>Gardenia jasminoides</i>	2
<i>Gomesa flexuosa</i>	1
<i>Hemerocallis citrina</i>	5
<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	5
<i>Hibiscus syriacus</i>	2
<i>Hippeastrum reginae</i>	2
<i>Hippeastrum reticulatum</i>	8
<i>Ipomoea Cairica</i>	1
<i>Ixora chinensis</i>	12
<i>Kalanchoe pinnata</i>	1
<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>	1
<i>Nerium oleander</i>	1
<i>Pachystachys lutea</i>	20
<i>Pelargonium inquinans</i>	18
<i>Pelargonium x hybridum</i>	7
<i>Petunia x atkinsiana</i>	17
<i>Pleroma heteromallum</i>	2
<i>Pyrostegia venusta</i>	1
<i>Rhododendron indicum</i>	2

Rosa Transmorrisonensis	4
Spathiphyllum wallisii	41
Tecoma capensis	1
Thunbergia erecta	1
Total	379

Anthurium andraeanum has the majority of growth (96 in total) due to some factors that were practically seen and one of them is the sunlight it receives. Since *Anthurium andraeanum* gets more sunlight due to its location, the faster its growth rate. This plant species is considered as a houseplant for it is durable and only requires little care. It prefers indirect bright light and can be kept in shady places making it adapt to the changing weather of Baguio City. It is also seen that the plant is very healthy considering the size of its green leaves about 20cm long. It can be propagated from leaves alone or can even root them in water.

Table 15 Number of Angiosperms Under Plant Families

Plant Family:	Number of Plant Species:
Acanthaceae	2
Alstroemeriaceae	1
Amaryllidaceae	3
Apocynaceae	4
Araceae	2
Asphodelaceae	1
Asteraceae	4
Begoniaceae	2
Bignoniaceae	2
Bromeliaceae	1
Caryophyllaceae	1
Convolvuceae	1
Crassulaceae	1
Ericaceae	1
Euphorbiaceae	1
Geraniaceae	2
Lamiaceae	3
Lythraceae	1
Malvaceae	2
Melastomataceae	1
Nyctaginaceae	1

Orchidaceae	2
Rosaceae	1
Rubiaceae	2
Solanaceae	1
Verbenaceae	1
Total:	44

- *Table 15 shows the Number of Angiosperms under 26 Plant Families.*

The plant family Apocynaceae and Asteraceae has the majority of growth due to their adoption of the abiotic and biotic components of the area. Water, air, light, soil nutrients, and the correct temperature coupled with affection and care are some of the reasons why it grows healthy and fastly. Some are trees, shrubs, and sometimes even herbs with simple leaves with bisexual and actinomorphic flowers. The plant species belonging to the family Apocynaceae, also known as the “Dogbane Family” are *Nerium oleander*, *Allamanda cathartica*, *Allamanda schottii*, and *Catharanthus roseus*. Plant species belonging to the Asteraceae family, also known as the “Daisy Family” are *Bellis perennis*, *Euryops chrysanthemoides*, *Erigeron sumatrensis*, and *Centaurea jacea*.

➤ *Thematic Analysis*

The inputs from the various interviews were processed into various codes and themes through thematic analysis. The themes that have been generated are the following:

➤ *Ways to Conserve and Preserve Flowering Plants:*

- *Use Main Ways of Conservation (in-Situ and Ex-Situ Conservation)*

To further understand this, In-situ conservation is the preservation of plant species in the natural state where they naturally occur. On the other hand, Ex-situ conservation or “off-site conservation” is the preservation of plant species outside their natural habitats.

- *Collection of Flowering Plants and Placing them in Cold Storage or Field Gene Banks*

Field gene banks are facilities that collect, catalog, and store samples of biological material and are used for laboratory research. It maintains small populations of plants in protected places.

- *Provide basic Needs*

Providing the basic needs of plants which are light, air, and water, makes them generate the glucose that they need in order to survive. Plants require these to properly grow.

- *Make use of Natural Pesticides*

Natural pesticides are biodegradable and less harmful to humans and animals. In addition to this, they are cheaper and more accessible to different countries.

- *Apply Proper Cultivation.*

Proper cultivation is adequate site preparation, it is achieved by not disturbing plant roots, loosening the soil only a couple of inches to optimize penetration of air, removing weeds, etc.

➤ *Advice and Recommendations in Conserving and Preserving Flowering Plants:*

- *Conserve Plants that are at Risk of Extinction*

The extinction of plants will have a ripple effect on the entire ecosystem. The extinction of plant species shows that the ecosystem is unbalanced and slowly falling apart. Thus, conserving these plant species will aid in maintaining the health of the ecosystem.

- *Promote Cultivation in Far Plant Areas to Save Old Varieties*

In order to conserve flowering plants, specifically the old varieties that are already at risk of extinction and are located in far plant areas, the promotion of proper cultivation in these areas will aid in conserving old varieties despite the introduction of new ones.

- *Study the Biodiversity of Flowering Plants before Conserving*

In order to successfully conserve a flowering plant, one must know its nature, properties, characteristics, and overall biodiversity, to properly decide on what method/s to use for the conservation and preservation of a certain flowering plant. Studying the plant before conserving is the basic premise of conservation.

- *Explore More Fields in Biology such as Taxonomy and Botany*

It is advised to study specialized fields rather than general ones such as botany, taxonomy, mycology, taxonomy of fungi, etc. to study more about the proper conservation and preservation of different species and be able to identify ways of conservation that will cater to the needs of every plant species.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study is concerned with naming, identifying, classifying, providing a brief botanical description, and suggesting ways how to preserve and conserve the flowering plants in Saint Louis School Inc. Indeed, SLSI is filled with a total of 43 vibrant plant species belonging to 26 families. It is composed of higher vascular plants reaching a total of 377 angiosperms present in the vicinity. The interviewees gave us recommendations and advice in taking the initiative in taking care of these angiosperms providing the necessary skills and attributes that are needed to be possessed as a future researcher that is willing to continue the study. Certain ways of preservation were discussed, wherein the subject of variety was introduced in which one interviewee mentioned that the number of species that are used as food diminishes because of a new species being introduced. Moreover, the summarization of what these interviewees discussed was to have full devotion and competency towards taxonomy or the interest in doing what needs to be done and to have a deeper understanding of how conservation works and the specificity of what kinds of plant species will be conserved. Correct handling and discipline should be applied when dealing with these angiosperms.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers were able to identify, classify, provide botanical descriptions, and suggested ways how to conserve and preserve the angiosperms in SLSI. However, there are still many suggestions and recommendations that the researchers provided for future researchers which are the following:

- The researchers were able to provide a plant care guide, however, providing a more specific guide that will cater to the different needs of the various flowering plants is highly recommended by the researchers. Since not all ways of conservation and preservation are effective for every plant species, the researchers recommend providing a brief plant care guide for each angiosperm that will sustain its needs.
- The research group recommends future researchers to further study and document the present gymnosperms and lower vascular plants like ferns for the reason that during the process of data gathering, the researchers have observed that there are also various non-flowering plants in the vicinity of SLSI.
- It is also recommended to study newly introduced flowering plant species in the vicinity of Saint Louis School Inc. for the reason that during the span of our research, there have been many introduced flowering plants even after we finished gathering our data.

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